

A Study of some Sulphonamidobenzimidazoles (BzH) as Metal Complexing Ligands. Part-III. Equilibrium Study of the Formation of Ternary M(Glycinate)(Bz) Complexes with Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

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Equilibrium study of the ternary interaction of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with glycinate (Gly^-) as the primary ligand and a few sulphonamidobenzimidazoles (BzH), viz. 2-*N*-benzenesulphonylaminoethylbenzimidazole (SMBzH), 2-*N*-benzenesulphonylaminoethylbenzimidazole (SEBzH) and 2-(1'-*N*-benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole (SMPBzH) as secondary ligands, by pH-potentiometric method at $30 \pm 1^\circ$, in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan medium and ionic strength 0.2 *M* (NaNO_3), provided evidence of formation of a variety of ternary complexes, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$, where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ; and $\text{Co}(\text{gly})(\text{H}_- \text{Bz})^-$, where $\text{BzH} = \text{SMPBzH}$. Stability of ternary $\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ complexes were found to be in the order, $\text{SMPBz} > \text{SEBz} > \text{SMBz}$, for the Bz ligands. Effects of electronic structure of the metal ions, multidentism of the BzH ligands, nature of the donor atoms, π -electron delocalisation in the metal-ligand bonds and intramolecular ligand-ligand stacking interaction on the stability of these ternary complexes have been discussed.

THE reactions taking place in the natural systems are highly specific and selective. Metal ions actively participate in most of the reactions occurring in the biological systems which are dominated by mixed ligand or higher order complexes involving multi-metal multi-ligand equilibria. The simplest system consists of a ternary complex, where one metal ion is coordinated by two ligands of different kinds, other than the solvent. Studies of such metal-ligand systems as models, have been proved useful in understanding the roles of metals ions in the biological systems¹⁻⁵ which are highly complex in nature. Sulphonamides and benzimidazole groups of compounds are well known for their antibacterial actions⁶⁻¹⁰. Sulphonamidobenzimidazoles having both sulphonamide and benzimidazole moieties in the same molecule, were found to inhibit the growth of many bacteria¹¹, and antibacterial properties of these compounds were found to increase to different degrees in the presence of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions.

With a view to elucidate the nature of biologically active forms of these compounds, systematic equilibrium studies on the ternary interaction of these metal ions with sulphonamidobenzimidazoles and typical (O,O), (N,O) and (N,N) donor ligands of biochemical origin have been undertaken. The present paper describes an equilibrium study of the ternary interaction of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II}

and Zn^{II} with glycinate ($\text{H}_2\text{NCH}_2\text{COO}^-$) (hereafter Gly^-) as the primary ligand and sulphonamidobenzimidazoles, viz. 2-*N*-benzenesulphonylaminoethylbenzimidazole (SMBzH), 2-*N*-benzenesulphonylaminoethylbenzimidazole (SEBzH) and 2-(1'-*N*-benzenesulphonylamino-3'-methylmercapto)propylbenzimidazole (SMPBzH) as secondary ligands,

by pH-potentiometric method at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan medium, ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3).

Experimental

The sulphonamidobenzimidazole ligands SMBzH, SEBzH and SMPBzH were prepared and purified by the literature procedures¹³⁻¹⁴. All the other reagents were of AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified dioxan¹⁵. Metal nitrate solutions and

carbonate free NaOH solution were prepared and standardised by the same procedures as described earlier^{12,16,17}. A series of solutions, each of initial volume 25 ml, in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan, ionic strength 0.2 M (NaNO₃) and having the following compositions, (i) 0.01 M HNO₃, (ii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.001–0.002 M metal nitrate, (iii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M GlyH₂⁺, (iv) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M BzH₂⁺, (v) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M GlyH₂⁺ + 0.001–0.002 M metal nitrate, (vi) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M BzH₂⁺ + 0.001–0.002 M metal nitrate, and (vii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M GlyH₂⁺ + 0.002 M BzH₂⁺ + 0.002 M metal nitrate, were prepared and titrated with a standard 0.125 M NaOH solution in the same solvent medium and having the desired ionic strength at 30 ± 1° (thermostated).

pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) using a special glass electrode in conjunction with an SCE. The pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions of pH 2, 4, 7 and 9.2, making appropriate correction for temperature. Analytical hydrogen ion concentrations at different pH meter readings were obtained by the usual procedure^{18–21} after incorporating correction for the use of mixed solvent using the pH-titration data of solution (i) and ionic product of water (pK_w = 13.86 at 30 ± 1°)²². Duplicate titrations were performed to check the reproducibility of the results.

Formation constants of proton–ligand and metal–ligand complexes were evaluated by executing the computer program SCOGS²³ (stability constant of generalised species) in an IBM 1130 computer in the Department of Computer Science, University of Calcutta. Two representative species distribution curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

It appears from the species distribution curves (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) that the free ligand species (Gly⁻) and its protonated forms GlyH and GlyH₂⁺

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves for Cu(Gly)(SMPBz) system: (1) GlyH₂⁺, (2) GlyH, (3) SMPBzH₂⁺, (4) SMPBzH, (5) Cu(OH)⁺, (6) Cu(OH)₂, (7) Cu(Gly)⁺, (8) Cu(SMPBzH)₂⁺, (9) Cu(Gly)(SMPBzH) and (10) Cu(Gly)(SMPBz).

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for Co(Gly)(SMPBz) system: (1) GlyH₂⁺, (2) GlyH, (3) SMPBzH₂⁺, (4) SMPBz, (5) Co(OH)⁺, (6) Co(OH)₂, (7) Co(Gly)⁺, (8) Co(SMPBzH)₂⁺, (9) Co(Gly)(SMPBzH) and (10) Co(Gly)(SMPBz)⁻.

prevailed in the pH ranges 7–10, 2.5–10 and 2–4.5, respectively. For the BzH ligands the free ligand anion Bz⁻ was practically non-existent at pH values less than 10, while the neutral BzH and the cationic BzH₂⁺ species dominated in the pH ranges 5–10 and 2–5.5, respectively. Deprotonation of BzH₂⁺ species involved the release of proton from the N⁺H benzimidazolium moiety, while that of BzH involved the release of the sulphonamide proton¹². pK^a values (Table 1) indicate that the successive deprotonation equilibria occurred at widely different pH values.

Hydroxo complexes, viz M(OH)⁺, M(OH)₂ etc. prevailed at pH ≥ 6 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} and at pH ≥ 4 for Cu^{II}. As the complexation equilibria were likely to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of metal ions the following species, viz. GlyH₂⁺, GlyH, Gly⁻, M²⁺, M(OH)⁺, M(OH)₂, M(Gly)⁺ and M(Gly)₂ were considered to exist in the binary complexation equilibria with the glycinate ligand. From the species distribution curves of binary systems, it appeared that the Cu(Gly)⁺ and Cu(Gly)₂ complexes were formed according to equilibria (1) and (2),

while for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}, the M(Gly)⁺ and M(Gly)₂ complexes were formed according to equilibria (3) and (4),

the charges being dropped for clarity.

The buffer region corresponding to deprotonation of BzH₂⁺ and BzH species occurred at lower pH values in the presence of these metal ions. With Cu^{II}, a deep blue complex, Cu(Bz)₂·2H₂O,

TABLE 1—PROTON - LIGAND CONSTANTS, METAL ION HYDROLYSIS CONSTANTS AND OF METAL - LIGAND CONSTANTS BINARY COMPLEXES AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$ IN 50% (v/v) AQ. DIOXAN MEDIUM, IONIC STRENGTH $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaNO_3)

(a) Proton - ligand constants							
$pK_{GlyH_2}^H$	pK_{GlyH}^H	$pK_{SMBzH_2}^H$	pK_{SMBzH}^H	$pK_{SEBzH_2}^H$	pK_{SEBzH}^H	$pK_{SMPBzH_2}^H$	pK_{SMPBzH}^H
3.25	9.50	4.18	10.30	5.03	10.93	3.92	10.05
(b) Hydrolysis constants of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} (aq.) ions							
$\log K_{Co}^H$	$\log K_{Ni}^H$	$\log K_{Cu}^H$	$\log K_{Zn}^H$	$\log K_{Co}^{2H}$	$\log K_{Ni}^{2H}$	$\log K_{Cu}^{2H}$	$\log K_{Zn}^{2H}$
-7.36	-15.51	-7.62	-15.88	-5.92	-12.00	-7.44	-16.42
(c) Metal - ligand constants of binary complexes							
Ligand	Constant	Metal ion					
		Co^{II}	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Zn^{II}		
GlyH	$\log K_{M(Gly)}^M$	5.70	6.51	9.42	5.71		
	$\log K_{M(Gly)_2}^{M(Gly)}$	4.17	5.63	7.63	5.11		
BzH-SMBzH	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	-	-	2.61	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	-	-	2.05	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^H$	-	-	4.25	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^{2H}$	-	-	8.95	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	5.01	6.13	8.46	6.19		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	4.93	5.64	7.85	5.80		
BzH-SEBzH	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	-	-	2.50	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	-	-	1.87	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^H$	-	-	4.55	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^{2H}$	-	-	9.58	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	6.31	6.41	8.63	5.80		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	5.48	3.51	8.02	5.18		
BzH-SMPBzH	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	-	-	2.78	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	-	-	2.20	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^H$	-	-	4.11	-		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^{2H}$	-	-	8.70	-		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)}^M$	5.10	5.23	8.48	6.27		
	$\log K_{M(BzH)_2}^{M(BzH)}$	6.05	4.67	7.88	5.90		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^H$	9.03	9.03	-	8.22		
	$pK_{M(BzH)_2}^{2H}$	18.48	18.58	-	17.02		

precipitated from solution around pH 4.5-5.0 at four moles of base per metal ion. With Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems, the buffer regions corresponding to deprotonation of BzH_2^+ were unaffected while those corresponding to BzH occurred at lower pH (5.0-7.5) with the release of two protons per metal

ion. Mole ratio study of Cu^{II} -BzH mixtures at pH ≈ 4.5 and of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} BzH mixtures at pH ≈ 7.5 indicated 1:2 metal-ligand complexes exclusively. Complexes higher than 1:2 were, therefore, disregarded in the computation of stability constants. Cu^{II} combined with BzH_2^+ , while

Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} combined with BzH species to produce ultimately the same type of complexes M(Bz)₂. As the complexation equilibria were likely to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of metal ions, the species BzH₂⁺, BzH, M²⁺, M(OH)⁺, M(OH)₂, M(BzH)²⁺, M(BzH)₂²⁺, M(Bz)⁺, M(Bz)(BzH)⁺, M(Bz)₂ were considered in executing the SCOGS program. For Cu^{II}, all the above complex species were found to exist in the complexation equilibria. For Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}, the complex species M(BzH)²⁺, M(BzH)₂²⁺ and M(Bz)(BzH)⁺ could not be detected in the species distribution curves.

Another buffer region with release of two more protons per metal ions were observed at a little higher pH value (8.5–10.5) in the M/SMPBzH binary systems, where M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}, but not with M/SMBzH or M/SEBzH systems. Had such a buffer region been due to the formation of ternary of hydroxo complexes of the type M(Bz)₂(OH)⁻, M(Bz)₂(OH)₂²⁻ etc., it would have been the feature of the other two systems also. The mercaptomethyl function (SCH₃) of the methionine side chain in the coordinated SMPBz ligand in M(SMPBz)₂ complexes definitely played some role in labilising the N₁H proton of the coordinated benzimidazole moiety, thereby making these complexes sufficiently acidic at pH 8.5–10.5 to release two protons to form two additional complex species, viz. M(H₋₁SMPBz)(SMPBz) and M(H₋₁SMPBz)₂. These two deprotonated complexes were, therefore, considered in the calculation of formation constants of the binary M/SMPBzH complexes with M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}.

The formation of ternary M(Gly)(Bz) complexes could be described by a series of equilibria of the following types,

Stability of ternary complexes of the type M(Gly)(Bz) could be characterised by $\Delta \log K_M$ values as defined by relation (8),

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log K_{M(Gly)(Bz)}^M - \log K_{M(Bz)}^M = \log K_{M(Bz)(Gly)}^M - \log K_{M(Gly)}^M \quad (8)$$

The complexes M(Gly)(Bz) and M(Bz)(Gly) were indistinguishable in labile systems like the present ones. $\Delta \log K_M$ values characterise the coordination tendencies of the ligand Bz⁻ towards binary

M(Gly)⁺ complexes (equilibrium 5), or of the ligand Gly⁻ towards binary M(Bz)⁺ complexes (equilibrium 6) relative to their coordination tendencies towards M²⁺ (aq.) ions as described by equilibria (9) and (10), respectively,

and ${}_{10}\Delta \log K_M$ stands for the equilibrium constant of the reaction,

and is related to the stability constants of M(Gly)⁺, M(Bz)⁺ and M(Gly)(Bz) complexes according to relation (12),

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log K_{M(Gly)(Bz)}^M - \log K_{M(Gly)}^M - \log K_{M(Bz)}^M \quad (12)$$

For the evaluation of formation constants, $\beta_{M(Gly)(Bz)}^M$ of ternary complexes by the SCOGS program, the following species, viz. GlyH₂⁺, GlyH, Gly⁻; BzH₂⁺, BzH; M²⁺, M(OH)⁺, M(OH)₂; M(Gly)⁺, M(Bz)⁺ and M(Gly)(Bz) were considered to exist in all the complexation equilibria. Additional complexes species, viz. Cu(BzH)²⁺, Cu(Gly)(BzH)⁺ in the Cu^{II}/GlyH/BzH systems and M(H₋₁Bz) and M(Gly)(H₋₁Bz) for M^{II}/Gly/SMPBz systems with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} were taken into account from a consideration of

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY M(Gly)(Bz) COMPLEXES AT 30 ± 1° IN 50% (V/V) AQ. DIOXAN MEDIUM, IONIC STRENGTH μ = 0.2 M (NaNO₃)

Metal	Bz ⁻ species	log K _{M(Gly)(Bz)} ^M	log β _{M(Gly)(Bz)} ^M	Δ log K _M
Co ^{II}	SMBz ⁻	4.83	10.53	-0.18
	SEBz ⁻	6.15	11.85	-0.16
	SMPBz ⁻	4.92	10.62	-0.18
Ni ^{II}	SMBz ⁻	5.49	12.00	-0.64
	SEBz ⁻	6.48	12.99	+0.07
	SMPBz ⁻	4.80	11.31	-0.43
Cu ^{II}	SMBzH	3.06	12.48	+0.45
	SEBzH	3.09	12.51	+0.59
	SMPBzH	3.68	13.10	+0.90
	SMBz ⁻	9.49	18.91	+1.03
	SEBz ⁻	9.81	19.23	+1.18
	SMPBz ⁻	11.18	20.60	+2.70
Zn ^{II}	SMBz ⁻	6.09	11.80	-0.10
	SEBz ⁻	5.71	11.42	-0.10
	SMPBz ⁻	6.17	11.88	-0.10

$$pK_{Co(Gly)(SMPBz)}^H = 8.92, \log \beta_{Co(Gly)(H_{-1}SMPBz)}^{Co} = 1.70.$$

the binary equilibria. However, deprotonation of the ternary $M(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ complexes to $M(\text{Gly})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{Bz})$ could be detected only in the case of $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Gly}/\text{SMPBz}$ system. All the constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values (Tables 1 and 2) corresponding to minimum standard deviation in the titre ($\pm 0.01\text{--}0.05$ ml) were used for calculating the species distribution curves (Figs. 1 and 2).

$M^{2+}(\text{aq.})$ ions and $M(\text{Gly})^+$ were the major species at low pH (2.0–6.5) while $M(\text{Gly})^+$ and $M(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ dominated at higher pH values (7.5–9.5). Appreciable amounts of $M(\text{Gly})^+$, $M(\text{Bz})^+$ and $M(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ prevailed at intermediate pH values in the ternary systems. In the ternary $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Gly}/\text{BzH}$ systems, the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{BzH})^{2+}$ complexes were practically non-existent in the pH range of formation of ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ complexes. Thus, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})^+$ was formed according to equilibrium (5) and $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ through deprotonation of $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})$. The deprotonation constant $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})}^{\text{H}}$ was, therefore, calculated from relation (13),

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})} = \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})} + \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})}^{\text{H}} + pK_{\text{BzH}}^{\text{H}} \quad (13)$$

where, the other terms have their usual meanings. Widely different values of $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})}$ and $\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})}^{\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})}$ indicated the formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{BzH})^+$ complexes in distinct steps.

Apart from the statistical reasons, the enhanced stability of ternary complexes as compared to those of the corresponding binary ones, *viz.* $M(\text{Gly})_2$ or $M(\text{Bz})_2$ in the cases to Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} arise mainly due to metal ion $\rightarrow \text{Bz}^- \pi$ -bonding involving the antibonding LUMO of the benzimidazole moiety and the filled d_{π} orbitals of the metal ions. The π -acidic nature of the sulphur ligand atom of the $-\text{SCH}_3$ moiety probably provided scope for an extensive delocalisation of electron density over a wider space, thereby caused the release of the N_1H proton of the coordinated SMPBz in the ternary $\text{Co}(\text{Gly})(\text{SMPBz})$ complex. Higher stabilities of ternary $M(\text{Gly})(\text{SEBz})$ complexes as compared to those of $M(\text{Gly})(\text{SMBz})$ probably arise due to greater flexibility^{26,27} of the SEBz series of complexes containing one five-membered and one six-membered chelate rings as against two five-membered chelate rings in the SMBz series. There was, however, no possibility of metal–ligand π -interactions in Zn^{2+} complexes.

Same $\Delta \log K_M$ values for all the three ternary $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{Gly}/\text{Bz}$ systems indicated the same type of bonding, *viz.* bidentate (N,N) chelation by all the Bz ligands to $\text{Zn}(\text{Gly})^+$. $\Delta \log K_M$ values of the

ternary $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Gly}/\text{BzH}$ complexes were all positive indicating the favoured formation of ternary complexes. Unusually large positive value of $\Delta \log K_M$ for the $\text{Cu}^{2+}/(\text{Gly})/\text{SMPBzH}$ complex was the result of an extensive delocalisation of π -electron cloud of the $\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{--Bz}^-$ bond over a wider space probably due to intramolecular stacking interaction^{26–30} (Fig. 3) between the aromatic π -system of the benzimidazole moiety and the vacant d_{π} orbitals of the sulphur donor atom of the $-\text{SCH}_3$ group of the methionine residue in SMPBzH.

Fig. 3. Stacking interaction in the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{SMPBz})$ complex.

It is interesting to note that, for the Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} systems, the ternary $M(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ species dominate in the region of biological pH (7.0–7.5). For the Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} systems, the binary $M(\text{Gly})^+$ species predominate in the region of biological pH and the ternary $M(\text{Gly})(\text{Bz})$ complexes occur at higher pH values. Such an observation is of tremendous biological significance in the context of nature's preferential selection of Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} as co-factors in many enzymatic processes, where the properties of the metal and also those of the enzyme proteins are often modified due to the formation of higher order metal–ligand complexes.

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